

EARTH SCIENCES

SMART-CITIES AS A VECTOR OF URBAN TRANSFORMATION IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract

The article reveals the features of the formation and functioning of modern smart cities. The authors draw attention to the main aspects of the development of these cities: the principles of sustainable development, the introduction of digital technologies into all spheres of society and local government, the conservation and efficient use of resources, ensuring the safety of city residents, etc.

Keywords: smart city, population, digital technologies, sustainable development.

Introduction. The development of modern cities in the global economic context is closely linked to the need to address an increasing number of complex challenges. With the growth of urban populations and the increasing expectations of residents and society, the concept of a “smart city”, based on the integration of information and communication technologies (ICT), has become one of the key achievements of the 21st century.

Today, cities around the world, regardless of size and age, are actively implementing “smart city” projects to improve the efficiency, sustainability and comfort of life of their citizens, while contributing to economic development. A particular challenge faces countries with a low or medium level of urbanization, which, in conditions of rapid urbanization, are forced to determine strategic priorities for the future development of their cities. Making these decisions creates both new opportunities and difficulties, because the quality of life of future generations will depend on modern approaches [1].

The successful development of cities in the future will be determined by their ability to implement the principles of a “smart city”. The use of innovative technologies and data analytics will help them effectively solve urban problems, improve the quality of services and promote sustainable development. As emphasized in the Smart City concept, ICT is an integral part of creating a favorable business environment, investment climate and ensuring comfortable living conditions for the population. Cities and agglomerations today are home to almost half of the world's population. However, the rapid growth of urban infrastructure leads to a deterioration in the quality of services provided to residents. Smart city initiatives are designed to solve these prob-

lems with the help of innovative technologies. Education, healthcare, transport, energy, waste disposal, employment and the fight against crime are just some of the key areas covered by the concept.

Main part. The idea of a “smart city” first appeared in the 1990s, although its formation can be traced back even earlier. Los Angeles is considered a pioneer in the introduction of new approaches to city management, where in 1974 they began to use computer technologies to analyze data on housing, transport, crime and poverty. The results obtained became the basis of urban development strategies [2].

In the 1980s, new approaches to urban planning continued to be implemented in various countries. For example, in Singapore, as part of the program to create an open computer network, the city took a significant step towards digital transformation. In 1997, the term “smart city” became more widespread, in particular through the implementation of large-scale projects in the Adelaide Technology Park (Australia) and in the cities of Cyberjaya and Putrajaya (Malaysia).

Currently, most cities in the world are at various stages of implementing projects aimed at implementing the principles of a “smart city” or adapting their individual elements. In parallel, equivalents of the term “smart city” are used, such as “networked city”, “information city”, “sustainable city” or “green city”, which focus on certain aspects of urban modernization.

According to the definition of the British Standards Institute (BSI), a smart city is a harmonious integration of physical, digital and human systems in a man-made environment, aimed at ensuring sustainable development, well-being and a high quality of life for its inhabitants.

It is worth noting that, according to statistics, the largest number of “smart cities” is in North America,

Europe and the Asia-Pacific region.

Over the past 2 decades, these regions have implemented the largest number of pilot projects, in particular those aimed at improving infrastructure.

There are two main ways to create a Smart City:

1. Building a "smart city" from scratch. This involves creating a city according to Smart City standards, taking into account the latest technologies from the very beginning. Examples of such cities are Masdar (UAE) and Songdo (South Korea).

2. The gradual introduction of smart technologies into existing urban infrastructure. This is the most common way to develop a Smart City.

Many future smart city projects that will be built from scratch are implemented according to the concept of the "15-minute city". The 15-minute city is an urban planning concept that involves ensuring the availability of basic needs and services, such as work, shops, education, healthcare facilities and places to relax, within a 15-minute walk or bike ride from any point in the city. The goal of this approach is to reduce dependence on cars, promote a healthy lifestyle, ensure environmental sustainability and improve the quality of life of city residents.

It is interesting that among large-scale, somewhat utopian projects, there are those implemented by private organizations or billionaires (for example, the Telosa City project conceived and planned for implementation by the former president of the e-commerce department of Walmart (USA) Mark Lohr). One of the most ambitious projects of our time is the creation of a high-tech city-region Neom - one of the largest and most complex construction projects in history. This project, initiated by the Crown Prince of Saudi Arabia Mohammed bin Salman (MBS), involves transforming a desert the size of Belgium into a "smart city".

The city of Neom is to become a key factor in the transformation of the economy of Saudi Arabia and a testing ground for innovative technologies that can change people's daily lives. The construction of one building within the framework of this project, according to some estimates, can cost up to 300-400 million dollars [2].

In Neom, it is planned to launch flying unmanned taxis and create an amusement park in the style of "Jurassic Park". The name of the city has a symbolic meaning: it combines the Greek word "Neo", meaning "new", with part of the Arabic term, which translates as "future".

The drivers of many changes in the field of "smart cities" are technology giants: Microsoft Corporation, Cisco Systems, Inc.; Schneider Electric SE; Siemens AG; and ABB Limited. Companies such as Honeywell International Inc.; Oracle Corporation; Huawei Technologies Co. Ltd.; Hitachi, Ltd.; and Intel Corporation are also quite actively involved in the development of solutions for "Smart Cities". Over time, the share of small companies occupying market niches and offering customized solutions with limited scope will increase. However, the market will still be dominated by technology giants. The industry is also marked by increasing cooperation between governments and companies to develop and implement pilot projects in the areas of urban surveillance, energy management, "smart"

transport and "smart" housing and utilities, etc.

The concept of "smart city" can be interpreted in different ways, but regardless of the approach, it should be considered as a high-tech integrated environment. Such a city combines modern technologies that contribute to the development of the social environment and entrepreneurship. Thanks to the digital transformation of sectors and the creation of a fully integrated intelligent infrastructure, it becomes possible to collect and analyze data in real time, as well as manage city services with the active participation of residents.

The concept of a smart city involves the integration of information and communication technologies, the Internet and the Internet of Things to manage the city economy. This includes information systems, transportation, energy, public and municipal services.

The concept of a "smart city" encompasses several key components:

- "Smart economy" – based on high-tech industries such as information and communication technologies (ICT), e-business and e-commerce. Its basis is to increase productivity and introduce innovations that contribute to economic growth.

- "Smart residents" – are educated, qualified and active citizens who participate in public life, contributing to the development of the city.

- "Smart governance" – involves the implementation of an e-government system that ensures effective interaction between citizens and authorities, creating a platform for social interaction of various institutions.

- "Smart mobility" – focused on innovative, safe and environmentally friendly transport systems. It uses ICT to optimize public transport and increase the convenience of residents' movement in everyday life.

- "Smart environment" – involves the integration of energy-efficient technologies and measures aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving the ecological state and preserving natural resources.

More detailed information about the factors of "smart economy", "smart" residents, "smart" management, "smart" mobility, "smart" environment and their characteristics are presented in the appendix to the PP of our master's research.

A smart city seeks to increase its competitiveness, ensure effective management of the urban economy and create safe and comfortable living conditions for residents. The main characteristics of such a city are technologically developed infrastructure, high-quality resource management, orientation towards economic efficiency, in particular urban environment services, as well as the creation of a comfortable and safe space with an emphasis on human needs.

The main elements of the functional system of a "smart city" are:

- a) data generated during the existence of a settlement in the conditions of digital transformation of the economy;

- b) technologies for their processing;

- c) decision-making mechanisms.

Data and software products are key tools for creating added value and the basis for managing technological processes.

To collect and process big data, the following important conditions must be met:

- technological equipment of the city: use of tools for recording and accumulating data that provide information collection on various processes in the city.
- data openness: free access to data (if necessary, in visualized form), which promotes transparency and accessibility for users at all levels.
- data compatibility: standardized approaches to data collection, storage, processing and transmission that allow integrating and analyzing multiple information flows simultaneously, ensuring effective interaction between different city sectors.

The main tool for creating “smart cities” is modern technologies and innovative services. It is about ensuring economic, social and environmental sustainability. However, each city chooses its own priorities in the direction of Smart development, since each of them has its own unique problems and features.

Innovative solutions for the urban environment include energy-efficient lighting, automated control of road and municipal equipment, automated rental and rental systems, and public Wi-Fi networks.

Smart urban transport is formed through intelligent public transport management. This involves optimizing traffic, creating a road condition monitoring system, implementing automatic recording of traffic violations, and organizing administrative parking spaces.

The public safety system is based on intelligent video surveillance, promptly informing citizens about emergencies, and monitoring the health of infrastructure in places of mass gatherings.

Environmental safety in the city is ensured by automating solid municipal waste management, an online monitoring system for the state of atmospheric air and water resources.

Urban management technologies are an integral part of the concept of a "smart city". They simplify the provision of public services through electronic document flow, digital signature, and automation of data collection and processing, which allows for the effective use of information.

A special role is played by identification technologies and digital financial solutions, in particular tax collections using blockchain or distributed registries. An important place in the development of the city is also occupied by 3D printing and 3D manufacturing, which are used in construction, product creation and

healthcare.

The components of a Smart city also include:

- fast and efficient collection and analysis of Big Data;
- systems for protecting users' personal data;
- implementation of public services in electronic format for the convenience of city residents.

Conclusions. Thus, SMART cities (smart cities) are a concept that integrates information and communication technologies (ICT) into the urban environment to improve the quality of life, increase resource efficiency and ensure sustainable development. Among the important aspects of the present that these cities broadcast, we can name:

- convenience for residents - intelligent transport, energy and utility management systems make life in the city more comfortable;
- safety - the use of technology for monitoring and responding to emergencies increases the level of safety;
- economic efficiency, which is realized through resource optimization, business support;
- sustainable development - the use of renewable energy sources and the reduction of CO2 emissions, waste management, etc.

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